

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:

Impacts on Climate and the Earth System

OCEAN ICE data catalogue system

Deliverable D7.8

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

<https://ocean-ice.eu/>

About this document

Deliverable: D7.8 OCEAN ICE data catalogue system

Work Package: WP7 Data Management

Delivery date: 22 September 2025

Type of document: Report

Dissemination level: Public

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1. Publishable summary

The OCEAN ICE project aims to assess the impacts of key Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean processes on sea-level rise, deep-water formation and global ocean circulation, thereby improving predictions of how changes in the Antarctic and Greenland ice sheets affect the Earth's climate. To achieve this, the project integrates historical datasets, new observations and advanced numerical models, including the development of coupled ice sheet–ocean and ice sheet–ocean–climate models.

Within this framework, the WP7 Data Management team builds on the legacy of the EU Horizon 2020 SO-CHIC project, ensuring that Southern Ocean data are made findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) for the long term. As outlined in the OCEAN ICE Data Management Plan version 2 (<https://zenodo.org/records/11096250>), WP7 focuses primarily on in situ data. Going beyond open access, OCEAN ICE actively implements open science practices. Its infrastructure is designed to guarantee immediate, free access to interoperable data, utilising open-source management tools such as ERDDAP™, GeoServer and GeoNetwork. All OCEAN ICE datasets are seamlessly integrated into EU public data repositories to maximise visibility and usability.

This document provides an updated inventory of data collections and products currently accessible through the OCEAN ICE catalogue. For completeness and to support the Southern Ocean Observing System community, it also includes a reference list of datasets available via SOOSmap2.

2. Data infrastructure

OCEAN ICE builds on and advances the data management framework underlying SOOSmap, an interactive web portal for oceanographic data visualisation and dissemination (Bordoni et al., 2024). SOOSmap was developed and is hosted by the European Marine Observations and Data Network (EMODnet) Physics for the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS), with support from the EU H2020 Southern Ocean Carbon and Heat Impact on Climate (SO-CHIC) project (Bricher et al., 2018; Goringe et al., 2021). The platform provides access to curated, standardised observation data from Antarctic and oceanographic research programs spanning multiple countries and scientific disciplines. SOOSmap organises data around individual observing platforms or sampling events (e.g., Argo floats or plankton trawls) and enables users to discover and retrieve circumpolar datasets from international research centres, data assemblers, repositories, and Antarctic marine infrastructures.

The OCEAN ICE data infrastructure, as described in Deliverable D7.4 (<https://zenodo.org/records/14193381>), is built around three interconnected layers: Data Layer (DL), Service Layer (SL), and Application Layer (AL). Together, they ensure that in situ observations are collected, standardised, published, and made accessible for both scientific and operational use.

The Data Layer manages the ingestion of:

- Near real-time data: measurements from global observing networks such as Argo floats, buoys and ships are transmitted within hours of collection. These data undergo automated quality control at global data centres (e.g., Coriolis, NOAA). They are synchronised with OCEAN ICE, where the DL enriches them with metadata and makes them publicly available.
- Delayed mode data: datasets that are scientifically validated and deposited in trusted repositories (e.g., PANGAEA, UK Polar Data Centre). The DL verifies formats, applies common metadata standards, assigns identifiers (e.g., DOIs) and republishes them in harmonised form for long-term FAIR-compliant access.

The Service Layer is powered by ERDDAP™ (<https://erddap.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/index.html>), which delivers data through APIs, enabling automatic integration into models, services and applications and GeoNetwork (<https://catalog.s4oceanice.eu/geonetwork/srv/ita/catalog.search#/home>) that provides a metadata catalogue for dataset discovery, search and retrieval.

In parallel, OCEAN ICE uses the Zenodo OCEAN ICE community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/oceanice/>) as an official platform for disseminating datasets and project outputs, ensuring their immediate accessibility and citability.

Finally, the main components of the Application Layer are:

- SOOSmap: maintained and updated by OCEAN ICE as part of its legacy from the SO-CHIC project. This makes OCEAN ICE data highly visible to the SOOS and international communities and enables users to explore ocean conditions.
- Jupyter Book integration (<https://s4oceanice.eu/demo/intro.html>): an innovative platform where each chapter is linked to executable Colab notebooks using OCEAN ICE data. These notebooks enable users to reproduce analyses, visualise the data catalogue, and interact directly with datasets.

This layered architecture ensures that OCEAN ICE data are FAIR, open, and usable at every stage, from observation to application. All datasets are published “*open by default*” under open licenses (CC-BY or CC0), which maximises their usability by stakeholders such as EMODnet and SOOSmap.

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3. Data catalogue

As already detailed in Deliverable D7.4 and previously mentioned in section 2, the OCEAN ICE data catalogue is composed of GeoNetwork, the OCEAN ICE Zenodo community, and it will also be accessible through a dedicated Colab notebook (https://s4oceanice.eu/demo/chapters/chapter1/oceanice_catalogue.html). In this chapter, the datasets available at the time of writing this deliverable are listed in the following tables.

Data collection and products

Name	Description	OCEAN ICE ERDDAP link	Link to source	Link to metadata	Link to DOI	Citation
Iceberg grounding enhances the release of freshwater on the Antarctic continental shelf	Output from 25-year ocean-sea-ice-iceberg simulations for Antarctica, including iceberg thickness, melt rates, grounding events, calving rates, and ice shelf thickness in netCDF format.		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15747365	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15747365	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15747365	Olivé Abelló, A., Mathiot, P., Jourdain, N., Kostov, Yavor, Holland, P., Gascoin, S., & Rousset, C. (2025). Olivé Abelló et al., 2025 dataset - Iceberg grounding enhances the release of freshwater on the Antarctic continental shelf [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15747365
			https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528376	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528376	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528376	Olivé Abelló, A., Mathiot, P., Jourdain, N., Kostov, Yavor, Holland, P., Gascoin, S., & Rousset, C. (2025). Olivé Abelló et al., 2025 dataset - Iceberg grounding enhances the release of freshwater on the Antarctic continental shelf [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528376
Contribution of continent-scale ice dynamics processes to freshwater fluxes	Spatially and temporally standardised freshwater fluxes from Antarctic ice shelves, including calving rates, basal melt rates, and integrated estimates,		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15590997	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15590997	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15590997	Millan, R., Barré, J.-B., & Moncada, F. (2025). Datasets of the deliverable D3.1 - EO: Contribution of continental scale ice dynamics processes to freshwater fluxes [Data set].

	based on open-source datasets.					Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15590997
Updates to the NEMO iceberg dynamics and grounding (Version 2).	Model code and input files for the simulations in Kostov et al. (2025), including code developed by Yavor Kostov to improve the iceberg dynamics and grounding capability in NEMO.		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15484879	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15484879	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15484879	Yavor Kostov. (2025). Kostov et al., 2025. Updates to the NEMO iceberg dynamics and grounding (Version 2). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15484879
FESOM 2. Circumpolar Simulation (1991-2020) / TS	Monthly mean potential temperature and salinity results from 1991 to 2020 south of 60°S.		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189061	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189061	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189061	van Caspel, M. (2025). FESOM 2. Circumpolar Simulation (1991-2020) / TS [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189061
FESOM 2. Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas Experiment (1991-2020) / TS	Potential temperature and salinity from 1991 to 2020 and south of 60S for the Bellingshausen and Amundsen Sea (BeAm experiment).		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15267996	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15267996	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15267996	van Caspel, M. (2025). FESOM 2. Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas Experiment (1991-2020) / TS [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15267996
FESOM 2. West and Shackleton Ice Shelf Experiment (1991-2020) / TS	Potential temperature and salinity from 1991 to 2020, and south of 60S West and Shackleton Ice Shelf Experiment		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268272	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268272	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268272	van Caspel, M. (2025). FESOM 2. West and Shackleton Ice Shelf Experiment (1991-2020) / TS [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268272
FESOM 2. Eastern Weddell Sea Experiment (1991-2020) / TS	Potential temperature and salinity from 1991 to 2020 and south of 60S Eastern Weddell Sea Experiment		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268317	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268317	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268317	van Caspel, M. (2025). FESOM 2. Eastern Weddell Sea Experiment (1991-2020) / TS [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268317
FESOM 2. West and Shackleton Ice Shelf Experiment (1991-2020) / UV	Meridional (vnod) and zonal (unod) velocity from 1991 to 2020, south of 60S West and Shackleton Ice Shelf Experiment		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299425	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299425	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299425	van Caspel, M., Janout, M., & Timmermann, R. (2025). FESOM 2. West and Shackleton Ice Shelf Experiment (1991-2020) / UV [Data set]. Zenodo.

						https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299425
FESOM 2. FESOM 2. Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas Experiment (1991-2020) / UV	Meridional (vnod) and zonal (unod) velocity from 1991 to 2020, south of 60S Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas Experiment		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299650	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299650	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299650	van Caspel, M., Janout, M., & Timmermann, R. (2025). FESOM 2. Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas Experiment (1991-2020) / UV [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299650
FESOM 2. Eastern Weddell Sea Experiment (1991-2020) / UV	Meridional (vnod) and zonal (unod) velocity from 1991 to 2020, south of 60S Eastern Weddell Sea Experiment		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299705	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299705	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299705	van Caspel, M., Janout, M., & Timmermann, R. (2025). FESOM 2. Eastern Weddell Sea Experiment (1991-2020) / UV [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299705
FESOM 2. Circumpolar Simulation (1991-2020) /UV	Meridional (vnod) and zonal (unod) velocity from 1991 to 2020		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15280675	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15280675	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15280675	van Caspel, M., Janout, M., & Timmermann, R. (2025). FESOM 2. Circumpolar Simulation (1991-2020) /UV [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15280675
Optimised Physical Tracer (OPT) reconstructions for past global ocean surface temperature, salinity and stable oxygen isotopes. (1.0)	Global ocean surface Optimized Physical Tracer (OPT) reconstructions of temperature, salinity and stable oxygen isotopes ($\delta^{18}O$) at past times reconstructed from modern interior ocean observations. Modern co-located observations of temperature, salinity and $\delta^{18}O$ from NASA-GISS (Schmidt et al., 1999) and CISE-LOCEAN (Reverdin et al., 2022) datasets were assimilated into a steady state observation-based circulation model, the		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15181349	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15181349	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15181349	Davila Rodriguez, X., McDonagh, E., Hamilton, B., & Gebbie, G. (2025). Optimized Physical Tracer (OPT) reconstructions for past global ocean surface temperature, salinity and stable oxygen isotopes. (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15181349

	Total Matrix Intercomparison (TMI; Gebbie and Huybers, 2010, 2012).					
NEMO4.2 eORCA1 configuration files for stable millennial ocean simulations (1.0)	Configuration files specific to the three model experiments described in the study entitled 'Effects of improved tidal mixing in NEMO one-degree global ocean model'. These experiments, called OLD, NEW and TRA, employ NEMO version 4.2.0 and the eORCA1 global mesh. They have been run for 1000 years under CORE version 2 normal year atmospheric forcing (https://data1.gfdl.noaa.gov/nomads/forms/core/COREv2/CNYF_v2.html).		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14041098	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14041098	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14041098	de Lavergne, C., Rathore, S., Madec, G., Sallée, J.-B., Ethé, C., Nasser, A.-A., Millet, B., & Vancoppenolle, M. (2024). NEMO4.2 eORCA1 configuration files for stable millennial ocean simulations (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14041098
Subglacial fresh-water discharge from the AIS into the Southern Ocean (D3.3)	This work quantifies basal melt rates in the Antarctic Ice Sheet caused by ice sliding , using surface velocity data to tightly constrain ice flow and bed stress estimates. Basal water production in fast-flow areas reaches meters per year , far exceeding melt from geothermal heat. A new subglacial water-routing algorithm was also developed, avoiding resolution issues of previous methods.	https://github.com/GHilmarG/UaSource	https://zenodo.org/records/14193326	https://zenodo.org/records/14193326	https://zenodo.org/records/14193326	Gudmundsson, H. (2024). Subglacial fresh-water discharge from the AIS into the Southern Ocean (D3.3). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14193326
Freshwater Sources in the Global Ocean through Salinity-d18O	This dataset contains point estimates of meteoric water and sea	https://zenodo.org/records/16992714	https://zenodo.org/records/16992714	https://zenodo.org/records/16992714	https://zenodo.org/records/16992714	Davila Rodriguez, X. (2025). Freshwater Sources in the Global Ocean through

<p>Relationships: A Machine Learning Solution to a Water Mass Problem</p>	<p>ice meltwater fraction in the ocean polar watermasses, as well as the global stable oxygen isotopic composition (d18O) of meteoric water. These estimates were inferred from co-located d18O, salinity and temperature observations from NASA-GISS (Schmidt et al., 1999) and CISE-LOCEAN (Reverdin et al., 2022) datasets, as well as individual cruise data available at the British Oceanographic Data Centre (https://www.bodc.ac.uk/), through the Self Organising Map machine learning approach to identify distinct salinity-d18O relationships in water masses. More information can be found in the associated manuscript, Davila et al. (2025).</p>					<p>Salinity-d18O Relationships: A Machine Learning Solution to a Water Mass Problem [Data set]. In Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16992714</p>
<p>Deployment of moorings in South Sandwich Trench (Milestone MS9)</p>	<p>IEnKS algorithm for initialising coupled ice - ocean models</p>	<p>https://github.com/RJArthern/KalmanEnsembling</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10868956</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10868956</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10868956</p>	<p>Abrahamsen, P. (2023). Deployment of moorings in South Sandwich Trench (Milestone MS9). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10868956</p>
<p>AUV observations under the sea-ice around grounded icebergs</p>	<p>High-resolution bathymetry data set, obtained with an AUV-mounted multibeam, in an ice-covered region near Bear Ridge in the</p>	<p>https://snd.se/en</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/13951229</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/13951229</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/13951229</p>	<p>Wählin, A. (2024). AUV observations under the sea-ice around grounded icebergs (D2.2). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951229</p>

	<p>Amundsen Sea. In total, 25 km² of high-resolution (1 m grid size) bathymetry were obtained. This can be compared to the resolution typically obtained from a ship-borne multibeam, which is 10-20 m. An initial assessment of the traces seen is also provided.</p>					
<p>Future freshwater fluxes from the Antarctic ice sheet</p>	<p>Yearly timeseries of the [5 25 50 75 95] percentiles for the calibrated probabilistic projections of Antarctic net mass balance, surface meltwater runoff, sub-shelf melt, and calving fluxes (in Gt/yr) for the Antarctic Ice Sheet under a SSP1-2.6 scenario</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SSP585_FWF_1990_2300_ZwallyBasins.html https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SSP126_FWF_1990_2300_ZwallyBasins.html https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SSP585_FWF_1990_2300_OceanSectors.html https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SSP126_FWF_1990_2300_OceanSectors.html https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SSP585_FWF_1990_2300_AIS.html https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SSP126_FWF_1990_2300_AIS.html</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14162776</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14162776</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14162776</p>	<p>Coulon, V., De Rydt, J., Gregov, T., Qin, Q., & Pattyn, F. (2024). Future freshwater fluxes from the Antarctic ice sheet [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14162776</p>

<p>AAD - ASPeCt-Bio: Chlorophyll a in Antarctic sea ice from historical ice core dataset (1983 - 2008)</p>	<p>The ASPeCt - Bio dataset is a compilation of currently available sea ice chl-a data from pack ice (i.e., excluding fast ice) cores collected during 32 cruises to the Southern Ocean sea ice zone from 1983 to 2008. Data come from peer-reviewed publications, cruise reports, data repositories and direct contributions by field-research teams. During all cruises, the chl-a concentration (in ug l-1) was measured from melted ice core sections, using standard procedures, e.g., by melting the ice at <5 °C in the dark; filtering samples onto glassfibre filters; and fluorometric analysis according to standard protocols [Holm-Hansen et al., 1965; Evans et al., 1987]. Ice samples were melted either directly or in filtered seawater, which does not yield significant differences in chl-a concentration [Dieckmann et al., 1998]. The dataset consists of 1300 geo-referenced ice cores, consisting of 8247 individual ice core sections, and including 990 vertical profiles with a minimum of three sections.</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/AAD_ASPeCt-Bio_historical.html</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/AAD_ASPeCt-Bio_historical.html</p>	<p>https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/ASPeCt-Bio</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.1029/2012GL053478</p>	<p>M. Meiners, M. Vancoppenolle, S. Thanassekos, G. S. Dieckmann, D. N. Thomas, J.-L. Tison, K. R. Arrigo, D. Garrison, A. McMinn, D. Lannuzel, P. van der Merwe, K. M. Swadling, W. O. Smith Jr., I. Melnikov, B. Raymond (2012) Chlorophyll a in Antarctic sea ice from historical ice core data. GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH LETTERS, VOL. 39, L21602, doi:10.1029/2012GL053478, 2012 https://doi.org/10.1029/2012GL053478</p>
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<p>AADC (2019) Extract of data from the sea ice measurements database - 1985-2007</p>	<p>Australian Antarctic Program - Dataset of fixed webcams in Antarctica</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/AADC_sea_ice_measurements_database_1985_2007.html</p>	<p>https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/sea_ice_measurements_database</p>	<p>https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/sea_ice_measurements_database</p>	<p>http://dx.doi.org/doi:10.26179/5cece40a20b0</p>	<p>These data were collected and made available by the SO-CHIC project and the programs that contribute to it</p>
<p>AMUNDSEN CRUISES DB</p>	<p>Collection of AMUNDSEN datasets.</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/AMUNDSEN_CRUISES.html</p>	<p>https://data.arice-h20.eu/</p>	<p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/ba56b242-00de-492c-99ca-2cd1fbd99bf https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6905b1bf-0562-4d22-8963-9c71f3f9bf21 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/5ecb7d3b-3802-4def-8e57-0988ea54498d https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/94d17e58-8769-4d07-ad9d-5864b08847c1 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/4f67a96a-ea9e-4ec1-bb16-157fbf7a59b0 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a11eac04-c967-4ea2-8ff3-c40ebc75c66f https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a11eac04-c967-4ea2-8ff3-c40ebc75c66f</p>		

				-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/9756a0fa-4d04-4cae-8e60-fcb600fe2e6b https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/b48e7870-278d-43fb-b735-1a589c6e2c3d		
Antarctic Tide Gauge Database	<p>The Antarctic Tide Gauge (AntTG) database provides tidal harmonic coefficients (amplitude and phase) for ocean surface height (tide-induced height perturbation relative to the seabed) at many coastal, ocean and ice shelf locations around Antarctica. The coefficients are provided for up to 8 tidal constituents (Q1, O1, P1, K1, N2, M2, S2, K2) where data is available. These coefficients are primarily intended for users interested in validation of tide models for the Antarctic seas, including the areas covered by the floating ice shelves (e.g., King and Padman, 2005; King et al., 2011; Stammer et al., 2014)</p>	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ANT_TG_OCEAN_HEIGHT.html	https://www.usap-dc.org/view/dataset/601358	https://www.usap-dc.org/view/dataset/601358	https://doi.org/10.15784/601358	<p>Howard, S. L., King, M., & Padman, L. (2020) "Antarctic Tide Gauge Database, version 1" U.S. Antarctic Program (USAP) Data Center. doi: https://doi.org/10.15784/601358</p>
ARCTICNET CRUISES DB	<p>Collection of ARCTICNET datasets.</p>	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ARCTICNET_CRUISES.html	https://data.arice-h2020.eu/	https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/ea0dee0a-a9ce-4d38-9f36-f0afc		

				<p>8718142 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/8df21a97-b47f-4346-be4e-5051e69af1af</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/33585efb-4aea-4dbe-a7e0-5d2335c320e4</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/bbd8bbcb-9-4cbb-4806-a066-b8e5c7c09845</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6c2742ae-b77f-4db1-a69e-7477884e5d4c</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/204acfc4-d955-47de-8f07-7cd41dc77151</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/ae859234-c0b4-429a-8ab4-1b9db71393e6</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/f02b5ec8-0155-42f2-a1f3-969c27130fb3</p>		
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Australian Antarctic Program Survey Webcams	Australian Antarctic Program - Dataset of fixed webcams in Antarctica	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/Australian_Antarctic_Program.html	https://www.antarctica.gov.au/antarctic-operations/webcams/			
British Antarctic Survey Webcams	British Antarctic Survey - Dataset of fixed webcams in Antarctica	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/British_Antarctica_Survey_webcams.html	https://www.bas.ac.uk/data/our-data/images/webcams/			
CCHDO Bottle Data	CCHDO GO SHIP bottle data from netcdf	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/CCHDO_Bottle.html	https://data.pmel.noaa.gov/generic/erddap/tabledap/cchdo_bottle.html			
CCHDO CTD Data	CCHDO GO SHIP ctd data from netcdf files	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/CCHDO_CTD.html	https://data.pmel.noaa.gov/generic/erddap/tabledap/cchdo_ctd.html	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3247384	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3247384	Henry, T., Robinson, C., Haumann, F.A., Thomas, J., Hutchings, J., Schuback, N.,

		dap/CCHDO_CTD.html				Tsukernik, M. and Leonard, K. (2019) Physical and biogeochemical oceanography from Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD) rosette deployments during the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE). (Version 1.0), [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3247384
CMEMS - CORA: Coriolis Ocean database for ReAnalysis	<p>The CORIOLIS Ocean Dataset for Reanalysis (hereafter "CORA") product is a global dataset of in situ temperature and salinity measurements. The CORA observations come from many different sources collected by the Coriolis data centre in collaboration with the In Situ Thematic Centre of the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS INSTAC). The observation integrated into the CORA product has been acquired by both autonomous platforms (Argo profilers, fixed moorings, gliders, drifters, and sea mammals) and research or opportunity vessels (CTDs, XBTs, and ferrybox). From the near-real-time CMEMS In Situ Thematic Centre product validated on a daily and weekly basis for forecasting</p>	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_OA_MY_013_052.html	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00351/46219/	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00351/46219/	https://doi.org/10.17882/46219	<p>Szekely Tanguy, Gourrion Jerome, Pouliquen Sylvie, Reverdin Gilles (2025). CORA, Coriolis Ocean Dataset for Reanalysis. SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/46219</p>

	<p>purposes, a scientifically validated product is created. It is a "reference product" updated on a yearly basis since 2007. This product has been controlled using an objective analysis (statistical tests) method and a visual quality control (QC). This QC procedure has been developed with the main objective of improving the quality of the dataset to the level required by the climate application and the physical ocean re-analysis activities. It provides T and S weekly gridded fields and individual profiles, both on their original level with QC flags and on the interpolated level. The measured parameters, depending on the data source, are: temperature and salinity. The reference level of measurements is immersion (in meters) or pressure (in decibars). CORA contains historical profiles extracted from the EN.4 global T&S dataset, World Ocean Atlas, SeaDataNet, ICES and other data aggregators.</p>					
<p>Collection of XBT performed on the high-density line IX28</p>	<p>The SURVOSTRAL program is a long-term study of upper ocean</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/table</p>	<p>https://campagnes.flotteoceanographique.fr/series/172/</p>	<p>https://campagnes.flotteoceanographique.fr/series/172/</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.18142/172</p>	<p>MORROW-GREINER Rosemary (1992) SURVOSTRAL, https://doi.org/10.18142/172</p>

<p>(Dumont d'Urville-Hobart) - 1990-2020</p>	<p>temperature and salinity changes in the Southern Ocean between Tasmania and Antarctica. These measurements contribute to the global XBT Network (High-density line IX28) and to the Global Ocean Surface Salinity programme. The programme started in 1992-93 and is based on high-density XBT measurements and continuous surface thermosalinograph measurements made onboard the French Antarctic supply ship, the ASTROLABE. The SURVOSTRAL programme is a co-operation between the IPEV and LEGOS (France), CSIRO (Australia), the Scripps Institution of Oceanography and NOAA (USA). It is an integral part of CLIVAR and the Southern Ocean Observing System.</p>	<p>dap/SURVOSTRAL.html</p>				
<p>CTD (data from NISKIN Bottles) LB21 ARCTIC Cruise Italian Arctic project CASSANDRA</p>	<p>Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD), Salinity, Dissolved Oxygen, Fluorescence, and Turbidity were collected during upcast profiles at discrete depths of Niskin bottle closure. Biogeochemical data were obtained from laboratory analyses of the water samples collected</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/IADC_ctd_cassandra_bottle.html</p>	<p>https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/f7474404-3331-43e5-883b-25755e94956d</p>	<p>https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/f7474404-3331-43e5-883b-25755e94956d</p>		

	<p>from Niskin bottles at discrete depths along the zonal transect at 75°N in September 2021. Project PRA CASSANDRA. Italian National Research Council - Institute of Polar Sciences data from a local source. The data originators are the CNR-Institute of Polar Science and the National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics, OGS, Trieste, Italy;</p>					
<p>CTD (DOWNCAST) LB21 ARCTIC Cruise Italian Arctic project CASSANDRA</p>	<p>Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD), Salinity, Dissolved Oxygen, Fluorescence, and Turbidity. Vertical profiles averaged every 1 meter along the zonal transect at 75°N. Project PRA CASSANDRA. Italian National Research Council - Institute of Polar Sciences data from a local source. Data originator is the National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics, OGS, Trieste, Italy.</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/IADC_ctd_cassandra_downcast.html</p>	<p>https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/c082c3ca-40bf-42b1-a61a-7b3697ab2c5a</p>	<p>https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/c082c3ca-40bf-42b1-a61a-7b3697ab2c5a</p>		
<p>CTD data set from mooring S1 @ 1000 m</p>	<p>Time series recorded at the mooring S1, at a nominal depth of 1000 m during different deployments. The scope of the measurements is to study the temporal variability of the thermohaline properties of the Norwegian Deep</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/info/IADC_s1_ctd/index.html</p>	<p>https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/2298c267-0e42-4bb8-8196-d2076fdf6d8e</p>	<p>https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/2298c267-0e42-4bb8-8196-d2076fdf6d8e</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.71761/2298c267-0e42-4bb8-8196-d2076fdf6d8e</p>	

	Water, and associated deep flow					
Daily Southern Ocean Sea Level Anomaly And Geostrophic Currents from multimission altimetry, 2013-2019	Sea Level Anomaly measured by Altimetry and derived variables	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/seanoeslev_anomaly_geostrophic_currents.html	https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/en/home.html			
ISAR L2 SST product	ISAR in-situ skin SST data, collected on the Marine National Facility, RV Investigator	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/DATA_TRAWLER_SST.html	https://marlin.csiro.au/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/bdf91f86-2968-4711-873e-2761383bb20Z	https://marlin.csiro.au/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/bdf91f86-2968-4711-873e-2761383bb20Z		ISAR-5D Procedures Manual at http://www.isar.org.uk/sites/isar/files/documents/Procedures_manual_v1.01.pdf , 18th GHRSSST Science Team Meeting extended abstract at http://imos.org.au/fileadmin/user_upload/shared/SOOP/SST_2016/Beggs_IMOS_Ship_SST_for_Satellite_SST_Validation_2017_11Jul2017.pdf , Wimmer, W. and I. Robinson, 2016: The ISAR instrument uncertainty model. J. Atmos. Oceanic Technol. at https://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/abs/10.1175/JTECH-D-16-0096.1s
MEOP - Animal-borne Profiles	MEOP (Marine Mammals Exploring the Oceans Pole to Pole) is a consortium of international researchers dedicated to sharing animal-derived data and knowledge about the polar oceans. Since 2004, several hundred thousands profiles of temperature and salinity have been collected by instrumented animals. The use of elephant seals has been particularly	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/MEOP_Animal-borne_profiles.html	https://www.meop.net/database/meop-databases/meop-ctd-database.html	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00343/45461/	https://doi.org/10.17882/45461	Please refer to https://www.meop.net/database/how-to-cite.html on how to cite these data appropriately.

	<p>effective in sampling the Southern Ocean and the North Pacific. Other seal species have been successfully used in the North Atlantic, such as hooded seals. These hydrographic data have been compiled into a quality-controlled database, known as the MEOP-CTD database. These data represent temperature profiles (°C). Each profile is located in space and time. It must be emphasised that the dataset of each individual CTD-SRDL has been edited and corrected separately, as a given CTD-SRDL has its own specificities in terms of data accuracy and quality of the estimated correction. A post-processing procedure is applied to hydrographic data in order to ensure the best possible data quality. For more details, please visit https://www.meop.net/database/data-processing-and-validation.html.</p>					
<p>Monthly climatology fields for product GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_PHY_001_030</p>	<p>Monthly climatology fields for product GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_PHY_001_030</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/GLORYS12V1_sea_floor_potential_temp.html</p>		<p>http://marine.copernicus.eu/documents/PU M/CMEMS-GLO-PUM-001-030.pdf http://marine.copernicus.eu/documents/QUID/CMEMS-GLO-QUID-01-030.pdf</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00021</p>	

<p>Network for the Collection of Knowledge on melt of Antarctic ice shelves (NECKLACE)</p>	<p>Network for the Collection of Knowledge on melt of Antarctic Ice Shelves (NECKLACE) is a SOOS-endorsed project which aims to collect a time series of observed basal melt rates from field instruments on ice shelves around Antarctica, primarily using autonomous phase-sensitive radar (ApRES). This will provide urgently needed control and validation data for models of ice shelf-ocean interaction, and a source of ground truth for satellite-derived estimates of average ice-shelf basal melt rates. NECKLACE is run by an international team of researchers, who provide a coordinating role. Research groups can contribute by procuring and deploying instruments in Antarctica. The NECKLACE team can assist with instrument setup, data processing, and archiving, and collates the resulting data to produce a coordinated basal melt rate product for end-users. The NECKLACE project seeks to collate data on ice shelf melt, gathered by research teams around the world. Results are</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/NECKLACE.html</p>		<p>https://necklaceproject.com/</p>		<p>Network for the Collection of Knowledge on the Melting of Antarctic Ice Shelves (NECKLACE). [YEAR]. Available at https://necklaceproject.com/. Accessed via soosmap.aq on [YYYY-MM-DD].</p>
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	<p>standardised and collated into a single data product that can be used by glaciologists, oceanographers, and ice sheet modellers to compare with their own results. By building on each team’s individual effort, we aim to create a continent-wide, open-access data product. Contributors include the British Antarctic Survey (BAS), the Australian Antarctic Division (AAD), the University of Tasmania (UTAS) and the New Zealand National Institute of Water and Atmospheric Research (NIWA).</p>					
<p>NOAA - Optimum Interpolation (OI) Sea Surface Temperature (SST) V2 High Resolution Dataset</p>	<p>The NOAA 1/4° Daily Optimum Interpolation Sea Surface Temperature (OISST) is a long-term Climate Data Record that incorporates observations from different platforms (satellites, ships, buoys and Argo floats) into a regular global grid. The dataset is interpolated to fill gaps on the grid and create a spatially complete map of sea surface temperature. Satellite and ship observations are referenced to buoys to compensate for platform differences and sensor</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/NOAA_OISST_v2.html</p>	<p>https://psl.noaa.gov/data/gridded/data.noaa.oisst.v2.highres.html</p>	<p>https://psl.noaa.gov/data/gridded/data.noaa.oisst.v2.highres.html</p>		<p>Huang, B., C. Liu, V. Banzon, E. Freeman, G. Graham, B. Hankins, T. Smith, and H.-M. Zhang, 2021: Improvements of the Daily Optimum Interpolation Sea Surface Temperature (DOISST) Version 2.1, Journal of Climate, 34, 2923-2939. doi: 10.1175/JCLI-D-20-0166.1 https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-20-0166.1</p>

	<p>biases. OISST belongs to a family of products that are sometimes referred to as "Reynolds SST" for Richard W. Reynolds, a NOAA scientist who worked to improve the accuracy of the SST analyses by optimising the advantages of in situ (ship and buoy) and satellite data. Older Reynolds SST products have been retired, except for the 1° weekly OISST. The dataset was developed using a methodology that includes bias adjustment of satellite and ship observations (referenced to buoys) to compensate for platform differences and sensor biases. This proved critical during the Mt. Pinatubo eruption in 1991, when the widespread presence of volcanic aerosols resulted in infrared satellite temperatures that were much cooler than actual ocean temperatures (Reynolds 1993).</p>					
<p>NOAA - Surface Ocean CO2 Atlas Database Version 2024 (SOCAT v2024)</p>	<p>The ocean absorbs one-quarter of the global CO2 emissions from human activity. The community-led Surface Ocean CO2 Atlas (www.socat.info) is key for the quantification of ocean CO2 uptake and its</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SOCATv2024_tracks_gridded_monthly.html</p>	<p>https://socat.info/index.php/data-access/</p>	<p>https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/metadata/landing-page/bin/iso?id=gov.noaa.nodc:0293257</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.25921/9wpn-th28</p>	<p>Bakker et al. (2016) & Sabine et al. (2013)</p>

	<p>variation, now and in the future. SOCAT version 2024 has quality-controlled in situ surface ocean fCO₂ (fugacity of CO₂) measurements from ships, moorings, sailing yachts, autonomous and drifting surface platforms, covering the global oceans and coastal seas from 1957 to 2023. The main synthesis and gridded products contain fCO₂ values with an estimated accuracy of better than 5 μatm. Sensor fCO₂ data with an estimated accuracy of better than 10 μatm are separately available. During quality control, marine scientists assign a flag to each data set, as well as WOCE flags of 2 (good), 3 (questionable) or 4 (bad) to individual fCO₂ values. Data sets are assigned flags of A and B for an estimated accuracy of better than 2 μatm, flags of C and D for an accuracy of better than 5 μatm and a flag of E for an accuracy of better than 10 μatm. Bakker et al. (2016) describe the quality control criteria used in SOCAT versions 3 to 2024. Quality control comments for individual data sets can be accessed</p>					
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	<p>via the SOCAT Data Set Viewer (www.socat.info). All data sets, where data quality has been deemed acceptable, have been made public. The main SOCAT synthesis files and the gridded products contain all data sets with an estimated accuracy of better than 5 μatm (data set flags of A to D) and fCO_2 values with a WOCE flag of 2. Access to data sets with an estimated accuracy of better than 10 μatm (flag of E) and fCO_2 values with flags of 3 and 4 is via additional data products and the Data Set Viewer (Table 8 in Bakker et al., 2016). SOCAT publishes a global gridded product with a 1° longitude by 1° latitude resolution without gap filling. A second product with a higher resolution of 0.25° longitude by 0.25° latitude is available for the coastal seas. The gridded products contain all data sets with an estimated accuracy of better than 5 μatm (data set flags of A to D) and fCO_2 values with a WOCE flag of 2. Gridded products are available on a monthly, annual, and decadal basis. Two powerful, interactive, online viewers, the Data</p>					
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	<p>Set Viewer and the Gridded Data Viewer (www.socat.info), enable investigation of the SOCAT synthesis and gridded data products. SOCAT data products can be downloaded. Matlab code is available for reading these files. Ocean Data View also provides access to the SOCAT data products (www.socat.info). SOCAT data products are discoverable, accessible and citable. The SOCAT Data Use Statement (www.socat.info) asks users to generously acknowledge the contribution of SOCAT scientists by invitation to co-authorship, especially for data providers in regional studies, and/or reference to relevant scientific articles. The SOCAT website (www.socat.info) provides a single access point for online</p>					
<p>Float deployment and data delivery to the community via ARGO servers (Milestone MS29)</p>	<p>Within the OCEAN ICE project, the deployment of six profiling floats, Argo ARVOR, perpendicularly to the Bransfield front area at the Strait has been implemented in March 2025. The floats dataset are quality-controlled and uploaded regularly with</p>	<p>https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/7902290 https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/2903996 https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/5907175</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/16628744</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/16628744</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/16628744</p>	<p>Shepel, N. (2025). Float deployment and data delivery to the community via ARGO servers (Milestone MS29). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16628744</p>

	the help of Coriolis and Euro-Argo to the https://dataselection.euro-argo.eu/ and https://www.ocean-ops.org/board	https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/3902667 https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/4903872				
OCEAN ICE - Argo DE - Deployment of 4 Argo float profilers	In the framework of OCEAN ICE, AWI deployed 4 ARGO float profilers in the Eastern sector of the Antarctic Shelf seas, next to the Amery ice shelf.	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ARGO_FLOATS_OCEANICE_DE.html	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00311/42182/	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00311/42182/	https://zenodo.org/records/13785339	Argo (2025). Argo float data and metadata from Global Data Assembly Centre (Argo GDAC). SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/42182
OCEAN ICE - Argo UK - Deployment of 4 Argo float profilers	In the framework of the OCEAN ICE project 4 ARGO float profilers were deployed by UKRI-BAS in the Amundsen and Ross Sea, in the Western sector of the Antarctic shelf seas.	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ARGO_FLOATS_OCEANICE_UK.html	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00311/42182/	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00311/42182/	https://zenodo.org/records/13785339	Argo (2025). Argo float data and metadata from Global Data Assembly Centre (Argo GDAC). SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/42182
OCEAN ICE - European circumpolar sea ice production fluxes	Projected freshwater fluxes from the Antarctic ice sheet under future climate scenarios, including meltwater and ice sheet dynamics data.	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/EU_circumpolar_seaice_prod_fluxes_1992_2023.html	https://gitlab.awi.de/ocean-ice/deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/11652686	https://zenodo.org/records/11652686	Kaleschke, L. (2024). EU project OCEAN ICE Deliverable: D1.4 Gridded European circumpolar sea ice production fluxes [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11652686
OCEAN ICE - Pan-Antarctic (90S-45S) temperature and salinity profiles compilation	This profile compilation contains conservative temperature and absolute salinity profiles computed from ship CTD, Argo floats, and seal-borne profilers in the Southern Ocean (90°S-45°S) since 1972, using the GSW toolbox. It provides an opportunity to investigate the broad-scale climatology of the Southern Ocean hydrography on and off	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/seanoe_ctempasal_profile_90S45S.html	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00886/99787/	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00886/99787/	https://zenodo.org/records/11096059	Zhou Shenjie, Dutrieux Pierre, Giulivi Claudia, Lee Won Sang, Kim Tae-Wan, Hattermann Tore, Janout Markus (2024). Southern Ocean (90°S-45°S) conservative temperature and absolute salinity profiles compilation (OCEAN ICE D1.1). SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/99787

	<p>the continental shelf and facilitate localised timeseries analysis of the variability across various timescales.</p>					
<p>OCEAN ICE - Pan-Antarctic (90°S-60°S) moored time series compilation</p>	<p>This mooring time series compilation contains temperature, salinity, and current velocity measured from a wide range of marine instruments in the Southern Ocean (90°S-60°S) since 1975. It provides an opportunity to investigate the broad-scale climatology of the Southern Ocean shelf dynamics and shelf connectivity of dense shelf water and freshwater propagation, and facilitate the timeseries analysis across various timescales.</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/seanoe_moored_time_series_south60S.html</p>	<p>https://www.seanoe.org/data/00887/99922/</p>	<p>https://www.seanoe.org/data/00887/99922/</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/11096059</p>	<p>Zhou Shenjie, Dutrieux Pierre, Giulivi Claudia, Silvano Alessandro, Auckland Christopher, Abrahamsen Povl, Meredith Michael, Vaňková Irena, Nicholls Keith, Davis Peter, Østerhus Svein, Gordon Arnold, Zappa Christopher, Sebaginazzi Dotto Tiago, Scambos Ted, Gunn Kathryn, Rintoul Steve, Aoki Shigeru, Stevens Craig, Liu Chengyan, Kim Tae-Wan, Lee Won San, Janout Markus, Hattermann Tore, Lauber Julius, Darelus Elin, Wählin Anna, Middleton Leo, Castagno Pasquale, Budillon Giorgio, Heywood Karen, Graham Jennifer, Dye Stephen, Hirano Daisuke, Miller Una Kim (2025). Southern Ocean moored time series (south of 60°S) (OCEAN ICE D1.1). SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/99922</p> <p>Zhou Shenjie, Dutrieux Pierre, Giulivi Claudia F., Jenkins Adrian, Silvano Alessandro, Auckland Christopher, Abrahamsen E. Povl, Meredith Michael P., Vaňková Irena, Nicholls Keith W., Davis Peter E. D., Østerhus Svein, Gordon Arnold L., Zappa Christopher J., Dotto Tiago S., Scambos Theodore A., Gunn Kathryn L.,</p>

						<p>Rintoul Stephen R., Aoki Shigeru, Stevens Craig, Liu Chengyan, Yun Sukyoung, Kim Tae-Wan, Lee Won Sang, Janout Markus, Hattermann Tore, Lauber Julius, Darelius Elin, Wählin Anna, Middleton Leo, Castagno Pasquale, Budillon Giorgio, Heywood Karen J., Graham Jennifer, Dye Stephen, Hirano Daisuke, Miller Una Kim (2025). The OCEAN ICE mooring compilation: a standardised, pan-Antarctic database of ocean hydrography and current time series. https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2025-54</p>
<p>OCEAN ICE - Trace gas measurements, basal glacial meltwater fractions, and water ages during RV POLARSTERN cruise PS124, Southern Weddell Sea</p>	<p>This dataset presents trace gas measurements and derived variables such as basal glacial meltwater (GMW) fractions and water mass ages from the RV POLARSTERN expedition PS124 in the southern Weddell Sea in austral summer 2021. The trace gases comprise the lighter noble gases, i.e., total helium (He) and the excess above solubility equilibrium ΔHe, the $3\text{He}/4\text{He}$ ratio reported as $\delta^3\text{He}$, total neon (Ne) and the excess ΔNe, and the deviation from the equilibrium He/Ne ratio $\Delta(\text{He}/\text{Ne})$, as well as the transient anthropogenic trace gases</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/Weddell_Sea_water_mass_age_meltwater_fractions.html</p>	<p>https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.971321</p>	<p>https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.971321</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/12581210</p>	<p>Huhn, Oliver; Janout, Markus A; Sültenfuß, Jürgen; Bulsiewicz, Klaus; Hinse, Yannik (2024): Trace gas measurements, basal glacial meltwater fractions, and water ages during RV POLARSTERN cruise PS124, Southern Weddell Sea, 2021 [dataset]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.971321</p>

	<p>chlorofluorocarbon (CFC-12) and sulphur hexafluoride (SF6) concentrations. From these noble gases (He and Ne), we derived glacial meltwater fractions. From the transient tracers, we computed SF6-concentration ages, CFC-12/SF6 ratio age,s and TTD (Transit Time Distribution) mean ages.</p>					
<p>Physical and biogeochemical oceanography data from Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (Bottle) rosette deployments during the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE)</p>	<p>This data set contains measurements from various sensors mounted on the Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD) rosette that was deployed in the Southern Ocean during the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE). 63 CTD casts were carried out during three legs in the period 21st December 2016 to 16th March 2017, including one test cast and one failed cast, for which no data is available. Data include temperature, salinity, pressure, dissolved oxygen, oxygen saturation, chlorophyll-a concentration, backscatter, and photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) and reported are also the computed variables</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ACE_bottle_CTD20200406CURRSGCMR.html</p>	<p>https://swisspolar.ch/expeditions/ace/ace-data/</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/3813646</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/3813646</p>	<p>Henry, T., Robinson, C., Haumann, F. A., Thomas, J., Hutchings, J., Schuback, N., Tsukernik, M., & Leonard, K. (2020). Physical and biogeochemical oceanography data from Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD) rosette deployments during the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE). (1.1). Zenodo https://zenodo.org/records/3813646</p>

	<p>density, depth, and sound velocity. All data has been quality-controlled and post-cruise calibrated, except for the oxygen data. Data is provided at 1 dbar pressure intervals for the up- and down-casts separately and as a merged bottle file when Niskin bottles were closed. This circumpolar data set provides insights into the circumpolar hydrography and biogeochemistry of the Southern Ocean during one austral summer season.</p>					
<p>Physical and biogeochemical oceanography data from Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD) rosette deployments during the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE)</p>	<p>his data set contains measurements from various sensors mounted on the Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD) rosette that was deployed in the Southern Ocean during the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE). 63 CTD casts were carried out during three legs in the period 21st December 2016 to 16th March 2017, including one test cast and one failed cast, for which no data is available. Data include temperature, salinity, pressure, dissolved oxygen, oxygen saturation, chlorophyll-a concentration,</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ACE_ctd_CTD20200406CURRSGCMR.html</p>	<p>https://swisspolar.ch/expeditions/ace/ace-data/</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/3813646</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/3813646</p>	<p>Henry, T., Robinson, C., Haumann, F. A., Thomas, J., Hutchings, J., Schuback, N., Tsukernik, M., & Leonard, K. (2020). Physical and biogeochemical oceanography data from Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD) rosette deployments during the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE). (1.1). Zenodo https://zenodo.org/records/3813646</p>

	<p>backscatter, and photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) and reported are also the computed variables density, depth, and sound velocity. All data has been quality-controlled and post-cruise calibrated, except for the oxygen data. Data is provided at 1 dbar pressure intervals for the up- and down-casts separately and as a merged bottle file when Niskin bottles were closed. This circumpolar data set provides insights into the circumpolar hydrography and biogeochemistry of the Southern Ocean during one austral summer season.</p>					
<p>POLARSTERN CRUISES DB</p>	<p>Measuring temperature and salinity profiles in the world's oceans is crucial to understanding ocean dynamics and their influence on the heat budget, the water cycle, the marine environment, and our climate. Since 1983, the German research vessel and icebreaker Polarstern has been the platform of numerous CTD (conductivity, temperature, depth instrument deployments in the Arctic and the Antarctic. We report on a</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/POLARSTERN_CRUISES.html</p>	<p>https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.860066</p>	<p>https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.860066</p>	<p>https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.860066</p>	<p>Rohardt, Gerd; Fahrbach, Eberhard; Beszczynska-Möller, Agnieszka; Boetius, Antje; Brunßen, Jutta; Budéus, Gereon; Cisewski, Boris; Engbrodt, Ralph; Gauger, Steffen; Geibert, Walter; Geprägs, Patrizia; Gerdes, Dieter; Gersonde, Rainer; Gordon, Arnold L; Hellmer, Hartmut H; Isla, Enrique; Jacobs, Stanley S; Janout, Markus A; Jokat, Wilfried; Klages, Michael; Kuhn, Gerhard; Meincke, Jens; Ober, Sven; Østerhus, Svein; Peterson, Ray G; Rabe, Benjamin; Rudels, Bert; Schauer, Ursula; Schröder,</p>

	<p>unique data collection spanning 33 years of polar CTD data. In total ,131 data sets (1 data set per cruise leg) containing data from 10,063 CTD casts are now freely available. During this long period, five CTD types with different characteristics and accuracies have been used. Therefore, the instruments and processing procedures (sensor calibration, data validation, etc.) are described in detail. This compilation is special not only with regard to the quantity but also the quality of the data - the latter indicated for each data set using defined quality codes. The complete data collection includes a number of repeated sections for which the quality code can be used to investigate and evaluate long-term changes. Beginning with 2010, the salinity measurements presented here are of the highest quality possible in this field owing to the introduction of the OPTIMARE Precision Salinometer.</p>					<p>Michael; Sildam, Jüri; Soltwedel, Thomas; Stangeew, Elena; Stein, Manfred; Strass, Volker H; Thiede, Jörn; Tippenhauer, Sandra; Veth, Cornelis; von Appen, Wilken-Jon; Weirig, Marie-France; Wisotzki, Andreas; Wolf-Gladrow, Dieter A; Kanzow, Torsten (2016): Physical oceanography on board of POLARSTERN (1983-11-22 to 2016-02-14) [dataset]. Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Bremerhaven, PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.860066</p>
<p>PSMSL - Absolute Sea Level Trend</p>	<p>"Since 1933, the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL)</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/PSMSL_Absolute_</p>	<p>https://erddap.socich2020.eu/erddap/files</p>	<p>https://psmsl.org/data/obtaining/complete.php</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.2112/JCOA</p>	<p>Simon J. Holgate, Andrew Matthews, Philip L. Woodworth, Lesley J. Rickards,</p>

	<p>has been responsible for the collection, publication, analysis and interpretation of sea level data from the global network of tide gauges. It is based at the National Oceanography Centre, Liverpool, United Kingdom and is a regular member of the International Council for Science - World Data System (ICSU-WDS). It is supported by the U.K. Natural Environment Research Council. The PSMSL reports to the International Association for the Physical Sciences of the Oceans (IAPSO) Commission on Mean Sea Level and Tides (President Prof. Gary T. Mitchum, USA). It is also a service of the International Association of Geodesy (IAG) and works with the Global Sea Level Observing System (GLOSS) and the Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS). The PSMSL receives monthly and annual mean sea level values from almost 200 national authorities, distributed worldwide, responsible for sea level monitoring in each country or region. Data from each station are entered directly as</p>	<p>sea_level_trend.htm !</p>	<p>/EP_ERD_SOO_BIOA_N_NN_J18/</p>		<p>STRES-D-12-00175.1</p>	<p>Mark E. Tamisiea, Elizabeth Bradshaw, Peter R. Foden, Kathleen M. Gordon, Svetlana Jevrejeva, and Jeff Pugh "New Data Systems and Products at the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level," Journal of Coastal Research 29(3), 493-504, (1 May 2013). https://doi.org/10.2112/JCOAS-TRES-D-12-00175.1</p>
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	<p>received from the authority into the PSMSL raw data file for that station (usually called the METRIC file in PSMSL publications)."</p>					
<p>SCAR - International Iceberg Database</p>	<p>In the period between the austral summers of 1982/83 to 1997/98, iceberg observations were recorded by most research vessels cruising Antarctic waters, under an international programme for systematic collection of Antarctic iceberg data initiated by The Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI) in 1981 with the endorsement of the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR). The resulting database contains records of 320,493 iceberg positions from 26,601 individual observations. Of these, 259,479 icebergs have been classified by size into five different length categories: 10-50, 50-200, 200-500, 500-1000 and >1000 m. The database also includes 8061 additional iceberg observations collected by the Australian National Antarctic Research Expeditions ships from 1984 (AAD), operating in the 50-150° E longitude</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/NPI_Iceberg_database.html</p>	<p>https://data.npolar.no/dataset/e4b9a604-1b64-4890-9f21-56b5589807c4</p>	<p>https://data.npolar.no/dataset/e4b9a604-1b64-4890-9f21-56b5589807c4</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.21334/NPOLAR.2021.E4B9A604</p>	<p>Orheim, O., Giles, B., Moholdt, G., Jacka, J., Bjørndal, A. (2021). The SCAR International Iceberg Database [Data set]. Norwegian Polar Institute. https://doi.org/10.21334/npolar.2021.e4b9a604</p>

	<p>sector. Some of these have been classified by slightly different size categories.</p>					
<p>SO-CHIC - Continuous meteorological surface measurement conducted during Cruise 2022 - AgulhasII</p>	<p>Continuous meteorological surface measurement conducted during the SO-CHIC (Southern Ocean Carbon and Heat Impact on Climate) cruise (December 2021/January 2022, S.A. Agulhas II). The cruise report is available at https://zenodo.org/record/6948850 for details.</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/SOCHIC_Cruise_2022_Agulhas_II_met.html</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/6948850</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/6948850</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/6948850</p>	<p>Ward, Brian, Azevedo, Alexandra, Binase, Zanele, ten Doeschate, Anneke, Els, Heino, Hamnca, Siyabulela, Jacobs, Leon, Katsoulis, Michael, Lavanchy, Sebastian, Lavis, Craig, Lourenco, Antonio, du Plessis, Marcel, Rosenthal, Hanna, Sallee, Jean-Baptiste, Soares, Bianca, Spira, Theo, & Steiger, Nadine. (2022). SOCHIC cruise report (Version v1). https://zenodo.org/records/6948850</p>

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5. Impact

With this deliverable, OCEAN ICE has contributed to the achievements of the following objective indicated in the description of the action.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

The present deliverable indicates if a dataset is already available in the SOOS system and enables us all to see progress in the coming years. With this deliverable, OCEAN ICE WP7 is taking over the legacy of the Horizon 2020 SO-CHIC project and is going to contribute to making Southern Ocean data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, long-term.